

Differential Peer-Group Affiliations on Psychosocial Adjustments of Adolescents in Enugu State, Nigeria

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<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4054148>

Abstract

The study investigated the differences in the psychosocial adjustment of adolescents based on the peer group to which they affiliate. Two research questions and two research hypotheses guided the study. It was carried out in Enugu state government owned secondary schools. The participants were selected through multi-stage random sampling technique. A representative sample of 2,219 SS2 students from the population of 27,775 SS2 students in the 314 public secondary schools formed the subjects of the study. Data were collected with two sets of questionnaires titled Peer Influence Questionnaire which was used to determine which peer-group values the participants affiliate to, and Psychosocial Adjustment Questionnaire which was used to measure the psychological and social adjustment levels of the adolescents. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested with t-test, at 0.05 level of significance. The major finding of the study was that the adolescents' psychosocial adjustment was significantly influenced by the types of values held by the groups they affiliate to. Based on the findings, recommendations were made which includes that adolescents should be properly guided in the act of peer-group affiliation. Psychological and social maladjustment tendencies seen at adolescent age should not be taken as "normal" adolescent behaviours which would be outgrown naturally.

Keywords: Peer-Group, Affiliations, Psychosocial Adjustments, Adolescents, Enugu State

Introduction

The adolescent child is like the yam tendril and the subtle shoot of a branch that needs special care and handling. The role of proper socialization of the adolescent child goes a long way to influence his/her total wellbeing. Among the many variables that influence the socialization of the adolescent are the family (parents), caregivers, and peers, among others. It is through the process of socialization which starts in the family, that the adolescent child is made socially adaptable to the society. Kazemi, Ashraf, Solokian, Soheila Ashouri, Elaheh; Marofi and Maryam (2012) opined that family is a place, in which skills are taught and the groundwork for

enhancement of personality and increasing of adaptability is laid. Within the family, adolescents understand their abilities, feel competent, and learn to adapt to new circumstances.

There is a saying that 'Today's child is tomorrow's adult' which, though may well be regarded as a stereotyped phrase, yet, expresses a profound truth. In Frieda Francisco-la Grange's epic opening address in a conference titled *Today's Child – Tomorrow's Adult*, he reflected on Alfred Adler's statement to the effect that the child is not merely a being but a *becoming*; undergoing fascinating and complex process of *becoming* an adult. However, it is necessary to state that if this complex process is not given special care and handling through proper socialization, the child of today may not become a fully functioning adult of tomorrow. Consequently, when the parents and significant others are dedicated to their role expectations in the family, school and neighbourhood, the adolescent child learns and invariably becomes well adjusted. What this means is that the quality of adaptation and level of adjustment of these adolescents are dependent on many factors which, in turn, also predict the developmental trajectories of the child.

No doubt, Okudo (2012) describes the adolescent period as a stormy stage of life as it is sometimes marked by turbulence and confusion. This informs why this stage should be consciously monitored and guided for an overall good of the members of this group. This stage calls for greater connection with parents, parental involvement in adolescents' activities and greater parental regulation of behaviour to achieve high levels of behavioural and academic adjustments, affiliation with the right peer groups, less substance use and ultimately higher level of psychological and social adjustments to make for a balanced adulthood.

For a concept to be psychosocial means it relates to one's psychological development in, and interaction with, a social environment. While the psychological aspect involves variables such as self-esteem, self-image/concept, self-perception, self-efficacy and optimism, the social aspect involves social relations, social status and inter relationship. Ezgi (2018); Poole, Cunningham and Schmidt (2020) hold that psychosocial adjustment is an important predictor of adaptivity during adulthood. Xiong, Li and Xia (2020) and Yunlong, Chengfu, Shuang, Junming, Yi and We (2019), all noted that parenting behaviours influence peer group affiliations which in turn, goes a long way to predict adolescents' psychosocial adjustment. Mina, Mana and Rekha (2018), also opined that parental marital status and adolescents' age group are associated with psychosocial problems. One reason for this peer influence is that adolescence is the period people of this group begin to break away from their families, to form friendships and affiliations which provide a platform for them to try out different roles and situations to figure out who they are and where they fit into the world. They spend more time with their friends/peers and less time with their families and as a result of these interactions, socialize and develop a sense of belonging, form lifestyle and norms that are suitable to them (Anierobi, Nwikpo, Okeke & Unachukwu 2019). As adolescence progresses, the importance of peer relationships increases dramatically. Teens spend proportionately less time with family and more time with friends, and these peer relationships become more intimate. Peer relationships provide an important context for learning and developing interpersonal skills that are necessary for both friendships and romantic relationships later in life (Connolly, Furman & Konarski, 2000), and on the other hand, can also

mark the beginning of sorrows and pains in later life (Gina, Margarida, Celeste, Ines & José, 2012). They observed that negative influence of the peer relationships is more connected to the involvement in risk behaviours. If peers play these significant roles in shaping the attitude and lifestyles of adolescents, there is, therefore, a need for attention to adolescents' relationships.

Following the above, it is reasonable to infer that peer group values directly influence the developmental achievements of the respective group members. Research by Donovan & Jessor cited in Nwiko (2016) found that peer group influences were continuous from adolescence to early adulthood. In this current study, the two peer-groups which are principle-oriented and acceptance-oriented anchor on the peer-group values to which the participants affiliate. The principle-oriented had peer groups that value conventional behaviours such as academic achievement, display of greater compliance with parental expectations, lower level of negative peer values, make a host of choice that in turn are the more proximal causes of the adolescent's decisions and opportunities at the transition to adulthood, continued to exhibit these same behaviors in early adulthood. Robins, Fraley, Roberts and Trzesniewski (2001) in their longitudinal study of stability and change in personality, noted that adolescents who were conventional in attitudes and peer affiliations in early to middle adolescence continued to exhibit these same attitudes and affiliations in early adulthood. Véronneau, Trempe and Paiva (2014) hold that friendships with prosocial and academically (adjustment) oriented peers are related to healthy development. Affiliation with peers holding adjustment values would not only be expected to increase the likelihood of higher educational attainment, this type of peer group also would be expected to reduce the likelihood of adolescent deviant behaviours such as substance use, truancy, cultism, weapon-carrying and many more(Nwiko & Ebenebe, 2014).

On the other hand, the adolescents who are of acceptance-oriented group, value social status, acceptance and popularity among peers. They are extremely concerned with image and social acceptance within the peer group. Some previous researches posited that adolescents in this group are involved in greater maladaptive behaviours like substance use, cultism, weapon-carrying, among others (Nwiko, 2016; Wallace, 2017). Some other scholars equally posited that adolescents who affiliate with deviant peers are at high risk for various aggressive behaviors including bullying perpetration (Mark & Buehler, 2012; Cho, Hong, Sterzing & Woo, 2017; Xingchao, Yixuan, Biao, Xiaochun & Lei, 2019). One factor found to foster a greater need for approval and acceptance from peer was a lower level of engagement with the family. These peers ultimately served as role models for substance and weapon-carrying/use. It was within the acceptance-oriented group that adolescents engaged in greater substance use and other delinquent behaviours (Vaughn, Perron, Abdon, Olate, Groom & Wu, 2012). Similar research shows that the need to gain social acceptance from peers resulted in greater alcohol use (Ramirez, Hinman, Sterling, Weisner & Campbell, 2012). They found that the reason for the alcohol use was to reduce feelings of anxiety and shyness in social settings which consequently fostered interaction among peers. Regarding cigarette use, Barton, Chassin and Presson (2011), reported that social image factors were motivators of initiating smoking during adolescence. This need to promote a social image that is appealing to peers is likely an indicator of seeking social acceptance

and social status among peers. Fuligni, Eccles and Barber (2001), also observed that youth and peer groups, heavily involved in substance use were extremely concerned with image and acceptance within the peer group.

Taken together, the previous research suggests that secondary school students' psychosocial adjustment is affected by influences emanating from multiple sources within adolescents' lives. Some of these influences (parents) have the potential to shape the nature of other influences (Peer affiliations); which in turn, affect lives and behaviours as well as factors that compete (substance and alcoholic use, weapon-carrying and use) with adolescents' general life. Furthermore, the works reviewed gave an understanding of how these key factors collectively influence psychosocial adjustments of adolescents by examining the developmental trajectories of youth.

Statement of the Problem

The adolescents of today are the adults of tomorrow. This explains the desire of every society to have well-adjusted adolescents to promote the desired virtues of good citizenship. Unfortunately, this seems yet, far-fetched, as every contemporary society still experiences numerous varieties of adolescents' unwholesome behaviours such as gross indiscipline, truancy, cultism, gun/weapon-carrying, violence, bullying and victimization, sexual molestation/rape and other behavioural problems seen in many ailing adolescents. The level of the manifestation of these psychosocial mal-adjusted behaviours remain a greater concern to stakeholders (educational psychologists, counsellors, parents, teachers and social workers, religious leaders etc), than for any other groups. The question is; what would have made these adolescents fail in these regards? This has made many researchers to look at different variables that might be responsible for this mal-adjustments, yet, evidence still shows that this problem remained unsolved. Some researchers such as Shephard and Green (2006), Okudo (2012) and Nwikipo (2016) have empirically sought to answer this pertinent question of why adolescents have a hard time adjusting psychosocially. The adolescents themselves, school and its environmental factors, the facilitators of knowledge (teachers), family etc had been factors considered, with some laudable recommendations made, yet, the problem remains unsolved. These current researchers, therefore, went beyond these, to study the types of peer group affiliation values these adolescents respectively hold and the influence these may have on their psychosocial adjustments. Responses of participants to items concerning their psychological and social levels were employed for the analyses of data. SS 2 students (2017/2018) in all the Enugu state government schools comprised the population of the study that cut across the urban and rural areas of the state.

The main purpose of this study was to determine the psychosocial adjustment levels of the adolescents affiliated with peers holding conventional/adjustment values vis-à-vis the ones affiliated to peers holding social status/acceptance and popularity values in government secondary schools in Enugu state. Specifically, the study sought to establish the difference in the psychosocial adjustment of:

1. Adolescents in acceptance-oriented group and those of the principle-oriented in psychological adjustment.
2. Acceptance-oriented group adolescents and of principle-oriented group in social adjustment.

The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses.

The questions which the researchers posed to guide the study are:

1. What are the mean psychological adjustment scores of acceptance-oriented students and their principle-oriented counterparts?
2. To what extent do the social mean adjustment scores of acceptance-oriented students and principle-oriented student vary?

The study hypothesized at $P < 0.05$ that there is no significant difference between the mean adjustment scores of:

3. Acceptance-oriented and the principle-oriented groups of students in psychological adjustment.
4. Acceptance and Principle-oriented groups of students in social adjustment.

Method

The study was conducted using a descriptive survey research design, because the entire population was not studied. A total of 2,219 SS2 students from the population of 34 schools chosen from a population of 27,775 students in 314 public schools which cut across schools in urban and rural parts of Enugu State (Enugu State Ministry of Education: Annual Census Report). Multi-stage random sampling technique was used in selection of the participants for the study. In the first stage, the 3 senatorial districts were purposively included. The researchers further selected 4 local governments from each of the 3 senatorial districts through simple random sampling. From each of the local government, 4 schools were selected at random and all the male and female SS2 students in each of the schools formed the sample of the study.

Data were collected with two sets of questionnaires titled 'Peer Influence Questionnaire' which was used to determine the peer-group values the participants are affiliated to, and 'Psychosocial Adjustment Questionnaire' which was used to measure the psychological and social adjustment levels of the adolescents.

To determine the convention/principle-oriented and social/acceptance-oriented adolescents, researchers designed an 8 item questionnaire while the second questionnaire which was to elicit information on the psychosocial adjustment of the respondents were equally constructed by the researchers from the items derived from the literature review of the study and based on the research questions. It was made up of 36 items in the ratio of 20 items for psychological and 16 for social adjustments respectively. Both questionnaires were face and content-validated by three experts of measurement and evaluation and educational psychology. Both the 8 and 36 item responses had the following values assigned thus:

1. Very important
2. Important

3. A little important
4. Not important

The reliability co-efficient of the instruments were established by collecting the data from 50 students from Nnewi, Anambra state. Their aggregate scores were calculated and then Cronbach alpha (δ) was used to determine the consistency of the items. The results showed reliability co-efficient scores of 0.72.

The researchers, with the help of their assistants, administered copies of the questionnaire to the respondents in the 48 schools in the 3 senatorial districts that made up the local government areas selected for the study. Prior to the administration of the questionnaire, the researchers had gathered the relevant materials and information, for instance the 2018 JSCE results. To be able to match the students' peer group affiliation responses correctly with each participant's responses to the items on the psychosocial adjustment questionnaire, each participant's number was smartly coded on the two questionnaires. This was done in that manner to make the participants feel free to respond as honestly as he/she can, without any suspicion of complicity. Form teachers and examination officers assisted in the administration of the copies of questionnaire.

Tallying and frequency distribution were used to sort those who are acceptance/socially-oriented and principle/conventionally-oriented. For the research questions, mean, standard deviation and variance were used to analyze the data. To test the two hypotheses, t-test was used to analyze the data.

Results

The data based on the research questions and hypotheses are presented in the following tables:

Table 1: The Mean Psychological adjustment Scores and Standard deviation of Principle-oriented and Acceptance-oriented Students.

Source of variance	N	X	S.D	Variance
Convention/Principle students	1,233	2.33	0.89	
Social status/Acceptance students	986	1.9	0.34	0.55

A cursory look at table 1 reveals that students who associate with peer groups which hold conventional/Adjustment values (ie principle-oriented values), obtained a mean adjustment score of 2.33 with standard deviation of 0.89 in psychological adjustment while their counterparts who associate with peer groups that hold social status values (ie acceptance and popularity) scored the mean of 1.89 with standard deviation of 0.34. This shows a variance of 0.55.

Table 2: Mean Social Adjustment Scores and Standard deviation of Convention-oriented group Students and Social status group Students

Source of variance	N	X	S.D	Variance
Conventional/ Principle students	1,233	2.39	078	
Social/Acceptance students	986	1.99	0.43	0.35

Table 2 shows that the mean social adjustment scores of students who affiliate with the peer groups that hold conventional values are higher than the mean adjustment scores of students who affiliate with peer groups that hold social status values.

Convention-oriented students had the mean score of 2.39 while social status-oriented students had 1.99 with a variance of 0.35.

Hypotheses

To test the two hypotheses that guided the study, t-test was used and are shown in tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: t-test Analysis on the Mean Psychological adjustment Scores of Convention-oriented and Social status group Students across group affiliations

Subjects	N	X	S.D	Df	t-cal	t-crit	p.05
Convention group students	1,233	2.39	0.78				
				2171	13.33	1.96	P>.05
Social status group students	986	1.99	0.43				

Table 3 above shows that at 0.05 level of significance and 2171 df, the calculated t-13.33 is higher than the critical t- 1.96. The hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore rejected and the alternative accepted. The result shows that there is significant difference in the mean adjustment scores of students that affiliate with convention-oriented peer group and those who affiliate with social status-oriented peer group in psychological adjustment.

Table 4: The t-test Analysis of the Mean Social Adjustment Scores of Convention oriented and social status-oriented students across peer group affiliation.

Subjects	N	X	S.D	Df	t-cal	t-crit	p.05
Conventional group students	1,233	2.33	0.89				
				2171	14.67	1.96	P>.05
Social status group students	986	1.89	0.34				

As evidenced from the t-test analysis in table 4, the convention-oriented valued peer group students did better than their social-status counterparts. At 0.05 level of significance and 2171 df,

the calculated $t=14.67$ is greater than the critical $t=1.96$. The hypothesis which says that there is no significant difference is therefore rejected and the alternative accepted.

Discussion

The findings of this study show that peer group affiliation in early and middle adolescence affects the psychosocial adjustment of the adolescents. The finding is in line with Xiong, Li and Xia (2020); Yunlong, Chengfu, Shuang, Junming, Liu and Wei (2019) who maintained that peer group affiliations goes a long way to predict adolescents' psychosocial adjustment. The data in the tables show that adolescents who engaged with peers valuing adjustment and right societal values, performed significantly higher than those who engaged with peers valuing greater social status among them in both psychological and social adjustments. This is also in consonance with Véronneau, Trempe and Paiva (2014) who hold that friendships with prosocial and academically (adjustment) oriented peers are related to healthy development. In other words, adolescents that affiliate with peers valuing adjustment, exhibit more conventional behaviours such as academic achievement, display of greater compliance with parental expectations and lower level of negative peer values, among others. On the other hand, and in agreement with (Vaughn, Perron, Abdon, Olate, Groom & Wu, 2012), it was within the acceptance-oriented group that adolescents engaged in greater substance use and other delinquent behaviours. This finding also collaborates that of Loke, Mak and Wu (2016) who, in their study to explore the relationship between peer pressure and the health risk behaviors of secondary school students, found out that peer conformity and peer involvement significantly correlated with the students' health risk behaviors, particularly with regard to smoking, drinking alcohol, and bullying. Friends who are involved in the same risk behaviors was the single most important factor associated with the participation of secondary students in those specific risk behaviours.

While the students who affiliate with peer groups holding adjustment-oriented values (wholesome behaviour-minded peers showed higher adjustment levels with mean scores of 2.39 and 2.33 respectively in psychological and social adjustments, the ones affiliating with peer groups holding social-status values (acceptance and popularity minded peers) scored 1.99 and 1.89 respectively. This result shows that early adolescence peer group affiliation is a factor predicting psychosocial adjustments. This is consistent with the prediction of Okudo (2012) that peer group affiliation goes a long way to predict adolescents' psychosocial adjustments which include among other things displaying of compliance with parental expectations, conforming to societal values and adjustments.

Conclusion

From the analysis and the discussions of the findings, the following conclusions were made:

- (1) The type of values held by the peer group which adolescents affiliate to, goes a long way to predict level of psychosocial adjustments and wellbeing.
- (2) Affiliation with peer group that holds right values, promote students' intra and interpersonal harmony.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and implications of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- (1) First, adolescents, especially those identified as affiliating with social status values, have to be trained in the art of making choice of friends.
- (2) Since it is a well established fact that the home is the first socialization centre, where foundation for children's future psychosocial and academic choices is laid, parents should be made aware, via forum like the Parents Teachers Association (PTA), on the importance of good parenting of their childhood. Enlightenment such as this, would empower the parents in their duty of guiding their children to make right choice of peers. When children choose the peer groups that hold worthy values, they will, in turn, promote their psychosocial wellbeing.
- (3) Adolescents should be properly guided in the art of peer-group affiliation, not just by their parents, but by all other significant individuals such as teachers and religious leaders.
- (4) Psychological and social maladjustment tendencies seen at adolescent age should not be taken as normal adolescent behaviours, which would be outgrown naturally

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